

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D3.7

Report on conclusions from multi-stakeholder taskforce

WP3 – Community-driven cross-infrastructure joint research - Medical

Lead Beneficiary: ECRIN-ERIC

WP leader: Jacques Demotes (ECRIN-ERIC)

Contributing partner(s): ECRIN, IRFMN

Contractual delivery date: 30 September 2017

Actual delivery date: 11 October 2017

Authors of this deliverable: Serena Battaglia

Grant agreement no. 654248

Horizon 2020

H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014

Type of action: RIA

Content

Executive Summary	3
Project objectives	3
Detailed report on the deliverable	3
Background	3
Description of Work	3
Next steps.....	4
Delivery and schedule	4
Appendices.....	4
Appendix 1: Publication: “Sharing and re-use of individual participant data from clinical trials: principles and recommendations”	4

Executive Summary

The aim of the taskforce is to develop procedures to provide the scientific community with access, upon request, to the patient-level data from previous clinical trials for re-analyses, secondary analyses and meta-analyses.

Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Produce a consensus document providing principles, recommendations and possible solutions for a secure clinical data sharing policy

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

Transparency and access to research data is a key feature for research policies, impacting on data quality and robustness of results, and leading to optimal use of data generated by research projects. This is of particular importance in clinical research, where access to individual patient-level data would ensure data quality and robustness of analyses, improve the accuracy of estimates of benefits from a treatment and optimize the use of clinical trials data for re-analyses, secondary analyses and meta-analyses. Various organisations have endorsed the principle of providing the scientific community with access to the patient-level data and several medical journals have similar request for the papers they publish. In spite of multiple discussion and a few pilot initiatives, a global consensus on principles and framework for the practical implementation of such a data sharing policy are still needed.

Description of Work

A taskforce composed of experts covering different fields in clinical data sharing (methodology, meta-analyses, clinical trials registration, public/charity funding bodies, medical journal editors, medicine agency, patient representatives, ethics committees, data protection regulation, intellectual property issues, IT) was set-up, to provide recommendations to make data sharing a reality.

Three meetings were planned (3-4 March 2016, Paris; 6-7 October 2016, Milan; 27-28 March 2017, Paris) and multiple issues were discussed following a Group Nominal Process methodology (a process involving problem identification, solution generation, and decision making, supported by an independent facilitator):

- Informed consent for re-use vs. broad consent or no consent (data protection regulation)
- Pseudonymisation vs. anonymization of data, and assessment of the risk of re-identification
- Open access vs. restricted/controlled access to data, scientific assessment of the request
- Format of patient-level data for storage and processing (e.g. CDISC standards)
- Data security and storage

- Type of repositories
- Possible IT solutions for data extraction (with or without download of data)

After the three meeting a consensus document describing the process in details and listing 10 principles and 50 recommendations was produced and submitted for publication to BMJ Open (currently under revision).

Next steps

The consensus document should serve as a guidance for data sharing in clinical trials.

As preparation for the next step (subtask 3.3.3) an environmental scan has been performed, evaluating existing repositories for data sharing. One of the major results of this activity was that promising repositories already exist and that developing a new pilot/demonstrator may not be necessary. In order to be able to judge whether an existing repository can really be used for sharing of IPD or an existing one can be adapted or extended to be compliant with the consensus document, the logical next step is to derive requirements, procedures and templates from the consensus document and to compare it with the procedures and functionalities of existing repositories. To that end, two main actions were identified:

- 1) Development of requirements, procedures and templates for patient-level data sharing
- 2) Specification of requirements for certifying repositories storing and managing patient-level data from clinical trials

At the end of the CORBEL project the outcomes of the whole task 3.3 should serve as a basis for the future development of data sharing services supporting both data generators and data users.

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Appendices

Appendix 1: Publication: “Sharing and re-use of individual participant data from clinical trials: principles and recommendations”

The paper was published in BMJ Open on December 14, 2017:

<https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/7/12/e018647>